

Development of an adhesive joint design and analysis tool

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Summary: The shear and peel stress distribution in a single-lap, tapered-lap and modified scarf joint between two isotropic adherends is analyzed using a linear elastic analysis. The analysis is incorporated into a computerized toolbox for joint design purposes. A finite difference method is used to solve the differential equations for the shear and peel stress distribution over the joint. Boundary conditions used limit the analysis to joints symmetric in material and geometry for the scarf joint case. The adherends are modeled as plates with extensional and bending stiffness bonded together with an elastic interlayer. The stresses across the adhesive layer are assumed to be constant. The single-lap results agree very well with Goland and Reissners'. The modified scarf joint shows significant reductions in adhesive stresses over the single and tapered lap configurations.

Keywords: adherend bending; peel stresses; blunt adherend tips; finite difference method; stress analysis; adhesive bond

1. Introduction

Adhesive joints have been widely used in automobile, aerospace and civil structures, as well as in the wood and plastics industries. However, there is no technique that is readily available to the design engineer for analyzing the wide range of possible joint configurations.

When it comes to designing practical joints used in industry many of the theories are very limited in use. Although some theories account for adhesive fillets, non-linear effects (high deflections and plasticity) and thermal effects, many still neglect other factors, such as manufacturing tolerances. Some of the theoretical joint configurations are almost impossible to manufacture in practice such as scarf joints with very sharp adherend edges. A designer needs quick answers to questions like what effect adhesive fillets, machining accuracy etc. have on the performance of a joint without having to perform long and tedious calculations. It would be very useful if much of the theoretical research on adhesive joints was made more applicable to joint design.

This paper reports progress in the development of an adhesive joint design and analysis tool with the above tasks in mind. The tool was initially started by van Tooreen and Roza [1] of Delft University of Technology, The Netherlands. The aim of the tool is to allow a full parametric analysis of adhesive joints between composite and isotropic materials with applications to analyzing joints in aerospace, automotive and civil structures such as bridges.

In designing a tool for computer applications ease and speed of use are essential. A finite difference method, has the advantage that many design variables can be incorporated into the analysis without too much complexity and can be run easily by a personal computer.

One of the most widely quoted papers in the literature on stresses in adhesive joints is that of Goland and Reissner in 1944 on single lap joints [2]. This paper was significantly

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important in drawing attention to the effects of adherend bending deflections on the peel and shear stresses in the adhesive layer. Despite the considerable efforts of a number of researchers over the last half-century, controversy and unresolved issues still remain. The failure load of adhesively bonded joints is still very hard to predict and analyses shows that joint strength continues to increase with increasing adhesive thickness where tests show an optimum at a finite rather small thickness. A difficulty that is encountered when performing analyses on single-lap joints is due to the geometric nonlinearities that arise from joint rotation and transverse deflection, which lead to cumbersome and time-consuming finite element models. The nonlinearities arise due to the eccentricity in the load path which creates a moment in the overlap region that is dependent on both the magnitude of the applied load per unit length and the joint rotation. Since the amount of rotation also depends on the load, the relationship between the load and rotation is nonlinear. The effect of these nonlinearities can be significant, and it is shown that, for typical failure loads, the error resulting from using a linear model instead of a nonlinear model can be up to 50%.

However, mathematical models can help a designer find certain advantages from one joint type to another. For instance the effect of adherend tapering on the joint stresses can be predicted. Under most operating loads and environmental conditions the adherends behave in a linearly elastic manner so that mathematical models are much easier to derive.

In terms of mathematical models, the single-lap joint is by far the most common configuration. Much of the work to be carried out on other joint configurations is still relatively new to the world of adhesive bonding. Hart-Smith, [3], has developed computer programs for analysing various joints, double-lap and single-lap, with equal to dissimilar adherends, for parallel, stepped, scarf and double-straps. However, these programs are intended for a specific application, that of aircraft construction, and may not be generally applicable to other aspects of the engineering usage of adhesives.

This report analyses the single-lap, tapered-lap and scarf joint depicted in fig. 1 but with a view to joint design in mind.

Fig. 1 Adhesively bonded configurations

Modifications are made to the basic text book joint configurations to include blunt adherend tips. Essentially the method presented is a modification of the Goland and Reissner analysis applied to tapered and scarf joints using the Hart-Smith bending moment reduction factor, [4] and solving the differential equations by a finite difference method.

2. Derivation of the governing differential equations

A free body diagram of the overlap region of the tapered-lap and scarf joint is depicted in fig. 2. The single-lap configuration can be found by suitable modification of the parameters on the tapered or scarf joint.

Fig. 2 Load equilibrium of the tapered (left) and scarf (right) region

T_{11} , M_{11} and V_{11} are the edge loads and are introduced here to simplify the analysis. For their determination the Hart-Smith k factor method, [4], was used to determine M_{11} , with V_{11} determined by equilibrium. In deriving the edge loads symmetric material and dimensional properties were assumed so that $M_{11} = -M_{22}$ (M_{11} and M_{22} will of course be different in an unsymmetrical joint).

$$M_{11} = k * T_{11} * \frac{e_i}{2}$$

and

$$V_{11} = -2M_{11} - T_{11} \cdot e_i$$

where e_i are the load eccentricities for the tapered joint, e_t , and scarf joint, e_s , defined in fig. 2. Alternatively the edge loads can be specified as the applied end loads.

2.1 Equilibrium equations

Consider segments, dx , of both the lower and the upper adherend under general loading conditions, fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Segments dx of upper left and lower right adherend of tapered (left) and scarf (right) joint showing sign conventions

Force equilibrium in the x and y direction and moment equilibrium about points A and B, yields the following 6 differential equations (shear and peel force centres are taken at the midpoint of the elements, point C). Setting alpha equal to zero gives the tapered/single-lap case.

For adherend 1:

$$\sum \overset{+}{\rightarrow} F_x = 0 \quad \frac{dT_1}{dx} + \sigma_a \cdot \tan \alpha - \tau_a = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum \overset{+\uparrow}{F_y} = 0 \quad \frac{dV_1}{dx} - \sigma_a - \tau_a \cdot \tan \alpha = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\sum M_A = 0 \quad \frac{dM_1}{dx} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \tan \alpha \cdot T_1 - V_1 - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \tan \alpha \cdot \left(t_1 + \frac{d}{\cos \alpha} \right) \cdot \sigma_a + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(t_1 + \frac{d}{\cos \alpha} \right) \cdot \tau_a = 0 \quad (3)$$

For adherend 2:

$$\sum \overset{+}{\rightarrow} F_x = 0 \quad \frac{dT_2}{dx} - \sigma_a \cdot \tan \alpha + \tau_a = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\sum \overset{+\uparrow}{F_y} = 0 \quad \frac{dV_2}{dx} + \sigma_a + \tau_a \cdot \tan \alpha = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\sum M_B = 0 \quad \frac{dM_2}{dx} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \tan \alpha \cdot T_2 - V_2 - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \tan \alpha \cdot \left(t_1 + \frac{d}{\cos \alpha} \right) \cdot \sigma_a + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(t_1 + \frac{d}{\cos \alpha} \right) \cdot \tau_a = 0 \quad (6)$$

The above six differential equations include a total of 8 variables giving a statically indeterminate joint. Additional equations are derived from compatibility considerations.

2.2 Compatibility equations

The differential displacements between the upper and lower adherend are related to the shear and normal strains in the adhesive by compatibility equations:

$$\varepsilon_a = -\frac{(u_1 - u_2)}{d} \cdot \sin \alpha + \frac{(v_1 - v_2)}{d} \cdot \cos \alpha \quad (7)$$

$$\gamma_a = \frac{(u_1 - u_2)}{d} \cdot \cos \alpha + \frac{(v_1 - v_2)}{d} \cdot \sin \alpha \quad (8)$$

2.3 Hooke's Law

Assuming plain strain for relating stresses in the adhesive to strain yields:

$$\sigma_a = \frac{E_a \cdot \varepsilon_a}{(1 - \nu_a^2)} \quad (9)$$

$$\tau_a = G_a \cdot \gamma_a \quad (10)$$

where G_a is the shear modulus and is defined in the appendix.

2.4 Engineering bending equations

Simple adherend bending is assumed in relating moment loading in each adherend at the specified coordinate, x , to the second derivative of the vertical displacement at that point:

$$\frac{d^2 v_1}{dx^2} = \frac{-M_1}{D_1} \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{d^2 v_2}{dx^2} = \frac{-M_2}{D_2} \quad (12)$$

where D_n represents the adherend plane strain bending rigidity per unit width, with suffix $n=1,2$ representing the adherend number and is defined in the appendix

The adherends are modelled as plates. With respect to bending, a plane strain condition is assumed which eliminates the effects of anticlastic curvature. With respect to in-plane behaviour i.e. response to axial loading, a plane stress state is assumed. The elastic stress-strain equation for the upper and lower adherend at the adhesive-adherend interface is then:

$$\frac{du_1}{dx} = \frac{1}{E_1 \cdot t_1(x)} \left[T_1(x) - \frac{6 \cdot (1 - \nu_1^2)}{t_1(x)} \cdot M_1(x) \right] \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{du_2}{dx} = \frac{1}{E_2 \cdot t_2(x)} \left[T_2(x) + \frac{6 \cdot (1 - \nu_2^2)}{t_2(x)} \cdot M_2(x) \right] \quad (14)$$

A total of 14 equations with 14 variables is now obtained.

2.5 Algebraic manipulation

To express all the equations in terms of adherend 1 properties, the following algebraic manipulation is required:

Substituting eqn (1) into (4) and (2) into (5) yield:

$$\frac{dT_2}{dx} = -\frac{dT_1}{dx} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{dV_2}{dx} = -\frac{dV_1}{dx} \quad (16)$$

Integrating (15) and (16) using the edge loads as boundary conditions yields:

$$\overset{+}{\sum} F_x = 0 \quad T_2 = T_{11} - T_1 \quad (17)$$

$$\overset{+}{\sum} F_y = 0 \quad V_2 = V_{11} - V_1 \quad (18)$$

Substituting eqns (6), (17) and (18) into (3) yield:

$$\frac{dM_2}{dx} = -\frac{dM_1}{dx} - \frac{dT_1}{dx} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot t_1 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot t_2 + \frac{d}{\cos \alpha} \right) + V_{11} - T_{11} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \tan \alpha \quad (19)$$

Integrating (19) using the edge loads again as boundary conditions yield:

$$M_2 = -M_1 - T_1 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot t_1 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot t_2 + \frac{d}{\cos \alpha} \right) + M_{11} + V_{11} \cdot x + \dots \\ \dots + T_{11} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot t_{11} - \frac{1}{2} \cdot t_2 + t_{44} + \frac{d}{\cos \alpha} \right) \quad (20)$$

where $t_{11}=t_1(0)$ and $t_{44}=t_2(0)$.

Substitution of equations (9) and (10) into (1), (2) and (3) yields the 3 differential equations (21), (22) and (23) below. The coefficients and constants in the equations are defined in the appendix. The fourth and fifth differential equations are derived differently for the tapered and scarf joint.

$$1. \quad \frac{dT_1}{dx} + c_1 \cdot \varepsilon_a(x) - c_2 \cdot \gamma_a(x) = 0 \quad (21)$$

$$2. \quad \frac{dV_1}{dx} - c_3 \cdot \varepsilon_a(x) - c_4 \cdot \gamma_a(x) = 0 \quad (22)$$

$$3. \quad \frac{dM_1}{dx} + c_5 \cdot T_1(x) - V_1(x) - \hat{c}_6 \cdot \varepsilon_a(x) + \hat{c}_7 \cdot \gamma_a(x) = 0 \quad (23)$$

For tapered and single-lap joint:

Substituting eqns (15)-(20) and (13)–(14) into the second derivatives of eqn (7) and first derivative of eqn (8) with $\alpha=0$ yield eqns (24) and (25):

$$4a. \frac{d \gamma_a}{dx} - \hat{c}_{18} \cdot T_1 - \hat{c}_{19} \cdot M_1 = \hat{c}_{20} \quad (24)$$

$$5a. \frac{d^2 \epsilon_a}{dx^2} - \hat{c}_{21} \cdot T_1 - \hat{c}_{22} \cdot M_1 = \hat{c}_{23} \quad (25)$$

For scarf joint:

Substituting eqns (15)-(20) and the second derivatives of eqns (13)–(14) into the *second* derivatives of eqns (7) and (8) yield eqns (26) and (27):

$$4b. \frac{d^2 \gamma_a}{dx^2} - \hat{c}_8 \cdot \frac{dT_1}{dx} - \hat{c}_9 \cdot \frac{dM_1}{dx} - \hat{c}_{10} \cdot T_1(x) - \hat{c}_{11} \cdot M_1(x) = \hat{c}_{12} \quad (26)$$

$$5b. \frac{d^2 \epsilon_a}{dx^2} - \hat{c}_{13} \cdot \frac{dT_1}{dx} - \hat{c}_{14} \cdot \frac{dM_1}{dx} - \hat{c}_{15} \cdot T_1(x) - \hat{c}_{16} \cdot M_1(x) = \hat{c}_{17} \quad (27)$$

3. Boundary conditions

The 5 differential equations above require 6 boundary conditions for the tapered/single-lap case, eqns (21)-(25), and 7 boundary conditions for the scarf joint case, eqns (21)-(23) and (26)-(27). Three of the boundary conditions on the upper adherend are related to the shear force, V_1 , moment force, M_1 and normal force, T_1 , which all equal zero at the free ends of the joint due to the free edge boundary condition. A further 3 boundary conditions come from the derivation of the edge loads, T_{11} , V_{11} and M_{11} .

For the scarf joint case the 7th boundary condition comes from assuming a symmetrical peel stress distribution. This choice limits the geometry of the scarf joint to symmetrical ones, including the material properties of both adherends, even under applied edge loads conditions. Mathematically, this condition is represented by:

$$\left. \frac{d\epsilon}{dx} \right|_{x=0} = - \left. \frac{d\epsilon}{dx} \right|_{x=L}$$

4. Numerical solution of the differential equations

To solve the 5 differential equations, a forward finite difference method was used to approximate the first and second derivatives. Although a central difference method is more accurate, a forward difference method simplifies the computation greatly. Accuracy can be increased by increasing the number of steps. A variable step distribution was used to allow more elements to be entered into the regions that show the greatest stress variation.

By writing the finite difference equations in the form $A \cdot \bar{U} = \bar{B}$ and inserting the boundary conditions a matrix with $5 \cdot N$ equations (N is the number of steps over the joint) is obtained. The unknown vector \bar{U} is calculated by inverting the matrix and multiplying it through with the vector \bar{B} .

5. Results and Discussion

Results were shown to compare well with Goland and Reissner's for the single-lap joint since the theory is essentially the same. No results in literature on comparisons for the tapered and modified scarf joint results under axial loading were found. As an application example of the toolbox a comparison of results for the single-lap, tapered-lap and scarf joint was made.

For design purposes, the overlap length is one of the important parameters of a joint. Therefore, it is useful to see the comparison in stresses between joint configurations of varying overlap lengths. Plots were made of the peel and shear stress versus overlap length for the three joint configurations, single-lap, tapered-lap and scarf joint. Fig 4 shows the results. The material properties and dimensions were symmetric, being, $T_{11}=500\text{N/mm}$, $E_1=20600\text{N/mm}^2$, $\nu_1=0.17$, $E_a=738\text{N/mm}^2$, $\nu_a=0.45$, $d=0.25\text{mm}$, adherend thickness, $t_{11}=5\text{mm}$ and adherend tip thickness for tapered and scarf case, $t_{44} = 1\text{mm}$. The non-tapered length of the tapered joint, L_1 and L_2 , was set to zero to minimise the peel stresses.

Fig. 4 Comparison of the shear and peel stress results of the single-lap, tapered-lap and scarf joint for varying overlap lengths

Fig 4 shows that below an overlap length of 25mm a sharp increase in peel and shear stresses is observed. However due to the very limited literature available on general joint configurations it is not known what the true peel and shear values are. A finite element comparison would be useful and will be considered for later work.

For overlaps greater than 125mm little difference is seen between the shear and peel stresses, indicating that for design purposes the easier to manufacture joint should be chosen.

6. Conclusions

The 3 joint configurations incorporated into the computerised toolbox allow an engineer to easily analyse the 3 joint types under elastic conditions. The ease and speed of use of this toolbox mean that results like the ones shown can be produced in minutes. The advantage of the toolbox is that specific design rules are not needed to design a joint. The results show that overlaps between 25mm and 100mm show a large variation in adhesive stresses from one joint type to another. Obviously changing the material parameters will change these bounds and the toolbox can determine these new bounds very quickly and easily.

It would be useful to know the true bounds of the analysis by using finite element methods or photoelastic experiment results. If necessary improvements in the analysis such as including more accurate bending equations for the adherends could be incorporated.

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Appendix A

Constants and coefficients

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_1 &= \frac{E_1 \cdot t_1^3}{12(1-\nu_1^2)} & c_3 &= \frac{E_a}{(1-\mu_a^2)} & \hat{c}_7 &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(t_1(x) + \frac{d}{\cos \alpha} \right) \cdot G_a \\
 D_2 &= \frac{E_2 \cdot t_2^3}{12(1-\nu_2^2)} & c_4 &= G_a \cdot \tan \alpha & \hat{c}_8 &= \frac{\cos \alpha}{d} \cdot (B_1(x) + B_2(x) + E_2(x) \cdot F_1(x)) \\
 c_1 &= \frac{E_a}{(1-\mu_a^2)} \cdot \tan \alpha & c_5 &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \tan \alpha & \hat{c}_9 &= \frac{\cos \alpha}{d} \cdot (-E_1(x) + E_2(x)) \\
 c_2 &= G_a = \frac{E_a}{2(1+\nu_a)} & \hat{c}_6 &= c_5 \cdot \left(t_1(x) + \frac{d}{\cos \alpha} \right) \cdot c_3 \\
 \hat{c}_{10} &= \frac{\cos \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{B_1(x)}{t_1(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha - \frac{B_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha - \frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha \cdot F_1(x) \right) - \frac{\sin \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot E_2(x) \cdot F_1(x)}{t_2(x)} \right) \\
 \hat{c}_{11} &= \frac{\cos \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(-\frac{2 \cdot E_1(x)}{t_1(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha - \frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha \right) + \frac{\sin \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(-\frac{2 \cdot E_1(x)}{t_1(x)} - \frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \right) \\
 \hat{c}_{12} &= T_{11} \cdot \left[\frac{\cos \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{B_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha + \frac{1}{2} \cdot E_2(x) \cdot \tan \alpha + \frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha \cdot F_3(x) \right) + \frac{\sin \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot E_2(x) \cdot F_3(x)}{t_2(x)} \right) \right] \\
 &\dots + V_{11} \cdot \left[\frac{\cos \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(-E_2(x) + \frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha \cdot x \right) + \frac{\sin \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot x \right) \right] \\
 &\dots + M_{11} \cdot \left[\frac{\cos \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha \right) + \frac{\sin \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \right) \right] \\
 \hat{c}_{13} &= -\frac{\sin \alpha}{d} \cdot (B_1(x) + B_2(x) + E_2(x) \cdot F_1(x)) & \hat{c}_{14} &= \frac{-\sin \alpha}{d} \cdot (-E_1(x) + E_2(x))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\hat{c}_{15} = \frac{-\sin \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{B_1(x)}{t_1(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha - \frac{B_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha - \frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha \cdot F_1(x) \right) - \frac{\cos \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot E_2(x) \cdot F_1(x)}{t_2(x)} \right)$$

$$\hat{c}_{16} = \frac{-\sin \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(-\frac{2 \cdot E_1(x)}{t_1(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha - \frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha \right) + \frac{\cos \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(-\frac{2 \cdot E_1(x)}{t_1(x)} - \frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{c}_{17} = & T_{11} \cdot \left[\frac{-\sin \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{B_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha \pm \frac{1}{2} \cdot E_2(x) \cdot \tan \alpha \pm \frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha \cdot F_3(x) \right) \pm \frac{\cos \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot E_2(x) \cdot F_3(x)}{t_2(x)} \right) \right] \\ & \dots + V_{11} \cdot \left[\frac{-\sin \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(-E_2(x) \pm \frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha \cdot x \right) \pm \frac{\cos \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot x \right) \right] \\ & \dots + M_{11} \cdot \left[\frac{-\sin \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \cdot \tan \alpha \right) \pm \frac{\cos \alpha}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot E_2(x)}{t_2(x)} \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\hat{c}_{18} = \frac{1}{d} \cdot [B_1 + E_2 \cdot F_2 + B_2]$$

$$\hat{c}_{19} = \frac{1}{d} \cdot [E_2 - E_1]$$

$$\hat{c}_{20} = \frac{1}{d} \cdot [-B_2 \cdot T_{11} - E_2 \cdot T_{11} \cdot F_1 - E_2 \cdot M_{11} - E_2 \cdot V_{11} \cdot x]$$

$$\hat{c}_{21} = \frac{1}{d} \cdot \left[\frac{-2E_2 \cdot F_2}{t_2} \right]$$

$$\hat{c}_{22} = \frac{1}{d} \cdot \left[-\frac{2E_2}{t_2} - \frac{2E_1}{t_1} \right]$$

$$\hat{c}_{23} = \frac{1}{d} \cdot \left[\frac{2E_2 \cdot F_1 \cdot T_{11}}{t_2} + \frac{2E_2 \cdot M_{11}}{t_2} + \frac{2E_2 \cdot V_{11} \cdot x}{t_2} \right]$$

$$B_1(x) = \frac{1}{E_1 \cdot t_1(x)}$$

$$B_2(x) = \frac{1}{E_2 \cdot t_2(x)}$$

$$E_1(x) = \frac{6 \cdot (1 - \mu_1^2)}{E_1 \cdot t_1^2(x)}$$

$$E_2(x) = \frac{6 \cdot (1 - \mu_2^2)}{E_2 \cdot t_2^2(x)}$$

$$F_1(x) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot t_1(x) + \frac{1}{2} \cdot t_2(x) + \frac{d}{\cos \alpha}$$

$$F_3(x) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot t_{11} - \frac{1}{2} \cdot t_2(x) + t_{44} + \frac{d}{\cos \alpha}$$

